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**Religion, Region, Language and the State
ERC SYNERGY PROJECT ASIA 609823
Project workshops 2017-2019**

This document provides a record of the Project Workshops organised under the leadership of Dr Nathan Hill (SOAS) during project period 3 (months 37 – 54, September 2017 to February 2019). As a rule, workshops have been held monthly except in the summer break (July and August).

September 2017

The Bactrian Archives as a Source for the History and Historical Geography of Afghanistan

Prof Nicholas Sims-Williams (SOAS, University of London)

Date: 12 September 2017 Time: 9:30 AM
Finishes: 12 September 2017 Time: 12:30 PM
Venue: Brunei Gallery Room: B104

From 1991 onwards, more than 150 documents in Bactrian, the principal administrative language of pre-Islamic Afghanistan, have appeared on the international art market. Many of these documents, for the most part legal contracts and letters, are dated in years ranging from 110 to 549 of an unspecified era. With them are associated some 32 Arabic documents dated in the years 138-160 A.H., some of which refer to persons who are also known from the latest of the Bactrian documents.

This presentation will be divided into three parts. The first will be concerned with the synchronisms which may allow one to establish the starting-point of the Bactrian era and thus to interpret the dates of the dated documents. The second will be devoted to evidence for the relative and absolute chronology of the numerous undated Bactrian documents, while the third will be an examination of the various regions of Afghanistan from which the documents derive.

Having established where and when the Bactrian documents were written, one can begin to make sense of the fragments of history which each of them contains.

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October 2017

Language in Early Burma

Dr Patrick McCormick (SEAJunction, Yangon), Dr Hideo Sawada (Tokyo University of Foreign Studies), and Dr Tilman Frasch (Manchester Metropolitan University)

Date: 10 October 2017 Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 10 October 2017 Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

Burmese Dialect Studies: the Dialectics of History and Ethnic Emergence

Dr Patrick McCormick (SEAJunction, Yangon)

This talk will discuss the Burmese dialects, the history of their study and what we currently know of them. The approach taken will be both that of a historian and of a linguist. What, if anything, does the state of these languages say about the history of these communities and their relation with the larger body of Burmese speakers?

Northern Burmish languages and Burmese

Dr Hideo Sawada (Tokyo University of Foreign Studies)

Northern Burmish languages, spoken in Kachin State and Shan State of Myanmar and Yunnan Province of China, are the genetically closest languages to Burmese. In this presentation I will introduce Northern Burmish languages such as Zaiwa (Atsi), Lacid (Lashi), Lhaovo (Maru) as well as Gyenno? and Tho?lhang dialects of Lhaovo, and Lhangsu language, which are still not well clarified. This talk will present their phonological systems and the correspondence between them and that of Burmese. This talk will also compare some aspects of grammatical system of Northern Burmish languages (especially Lhaovo) with those of Burmese.

Some Putative Pyu Loan Words in Old Burmese

Dr Tilman Frasch (Manchester Metropolitan University)

The relationship between the Pyu people, possibly the porters of Burma's earliest urban civilization (1st-9th centuries CE), and their Burman successors from the kingdom of Bagan (11th-13th centuries CE) is still a controversial matter. One possible scenario is that of a cultural continuum from the stone age men through the Pyu to the Burmans of Bagan; an alternative version assumes some kind of immigration from Central Asia into Burma/Myanmar, which could have occurred either before or after the Pyu period. The former case would make the Pyu a kind of first-wave immigrants or proto-Burmans, the latter places them at the end of an indigenous development superseded (and in fact terminated) by the immigrating Burmans.

There can be no doubt about the pastoralist and cattle-breeding past of the Burmans – not last, they frequently used the expression “may you go where the grass is green and the water clear” when releasing a person from serfdom. Quite in contrast to this cultural imprint, the Bagan kingdom that formed the environment for the proverb, owed its strength and stability to the cultivation of wet-rice based on large-scale irrigation works. However, terms and phrases relating to agriculture, frequently as they occur in the inscriptions from Bagan, have hardly ever been properly studied; in fact, many of

10:30am Dr Jason Hawkes (British Museum), "Data management in *Land, Settlement and Society: the Archaeology of Societal Transformations During the Gupta Era*"

11am Coffee break

11:30am Dr Donald Sturgeon (Harvard), "Data management in the Chinese Text Project"

12pm Dr Dániel Balogh (British Museum), "Digital adventures in Indic epigraphy"

12:30pm Dr Gergely Hidas (British Museum), "Data management in the critical edition of Sanskrit manuscripts"

1pm Lunch

2:30pm Prof Friederike Luepke (SOAS), "Data management in *Crossroads: Investigating the Unexplored Side of Multilingualism*"

3pm Jack Clift (SOAS), "Data management in *Multilingual Locals and Significant Geographies*"

3:30pm Helen Porter (SOAS), "Funder guidelines on data management"

4pm Tea break

4:30pm Prof Jonathan Silk (Leiden), "Closing remarks"

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December 2017

Money Supply, Quantity Theory, and Feudalism in Sixth Century India

Dr Robert Bracey (British Museum)

Date: 12 December 2017 Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 12 December 2017 Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

The feudalism hypothesis first proposed by G B Sharma in connection with copper plate charters has enjoyed considerable prominence in the historiography of South Asia. Sharma argued that in the mid to late first millennium AD a pan-Indian shift took place, with monetised urban market economies being displaced by redistributive activities that tied people to the land. He structured his account of this in terms of Marxist models of the feudal stage of development. Centrally important to this, and counter-arguments, are assumptions about the availability of money. Sharma has argued that there was a paucity of metallic coinage, and critics (particular Shailendra Bhandare) have argued there was not. While Sharma's methodology has been shown to be unsound that is not the same as demonstrating that his conclusion is wrong. This presentation will focus on the period between the death of Buddhagupta (c. AD 500) and the accession of Harsha (c. AD 600) which is widely assumed to be a period when metallic currency was in particularly short supply, due to political instability. It will explore what we know, and do not know, about coinage in that period, how coinage relates to money supply, and the applicability of modern economic theory - particularly issues around velocity, the aggregate quantity of transactions, price indexes, and the limitations/capability of our sources in addressing these issues.

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January 2018

Jainism

Dr Andrew Ollett (Harvard), Prof Paul Dundas (Edinburgh), and Lucas den Boer (Leiden)

Date: 9 January 2018	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 9 January 2018	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings	Room: 116

The Languages of Jainism in the Gupta Period

Dr Andrew Ollett (Harvard)

Before the Gupta period, Jains had used different varieties of Middle Indic for transmitting their scripture, commenting on them, and composing original works of literature and systematic thought. Among these varieties, we can distinguish first of all *Ardhamāgadhī*, the language of the *aṅgas*, and then two additional languages, both called *Prakrit*, which began to be used around the first century CE; one of these, called Mahārāṣṭrī Prakrit at a somewhat later period, was used for the *niryuktis* (versified commentaries on the *aṅgas*), and another—which, having had no more specific designation than "Prakrit" at the time that it was used, has been called "Śaurasēnī Prakrit" by modern scholars in order to differentiate it from Mahārāṣṭrī Prakrit—was used for the doctrinal and philosophical works of the Digambaras. In this workshop we will examine the changes in language use that were introduced among Jain communities in the Gupta period. We will discuss, first of all, the introduction of Sanskrit and the "standardization" of the aforementioned Middle Indic languages, and then we will ask what significance Jainism's use of multiple languages had, what the relationship between these various languages was imagined to be, and what the "division of labor" between these languages was.

A Legal Term in Haribhadra Yākinīputra's Ṣoḍaśakaparakaraṇa and its Implications Paul Dundas (Edinburgh)

Significant questions remain to be answered concerning Jainism as a social phenomenon during the Gupta period. A recent study by the speaker based on reading between the lines of the available patchy evidence offered some new interpretations of the actualities of the Jain community's status under the Guptas. This talk will amplify the aforementioned study by focussing on the means by which the Jain renunciant community was supported at this time. It will consider the role of financial endowment in the light of the few identifiable Jain sources (inscriptional and non-inscriptional) referring to this important legal mechanism which is mentioned frequently in Buddhist and Hindu texts of varying types. The talk will conclude with some conjectures about the significance of Prakrit references to the miraculous feeding of renunciants.

Umāsvāti's Tattvārthasūtra and the Gupta Period Lucas den Boer (Leiden)

The *Tattvārthasūtra* is the first systematic compendium of Jaina doctrine, and is still regarded as an authoritative overview of the Jaina tenets by contemporary Jains. We

do not know exactly when and where it was composed but there are good reasons to situate the text and the first commentary, the *Tattvārthasūtrabhāṣya*, in the Gupta Period. The *Tattvārthasūtra* was the first Jaina treatise that favoured Sanskrit over Prakrit, which seems to be a sign that the author of the text tried to connect to a wider intellectual milieu. In my presentation, I will discuss what the *Tattvārthasūtra* and the *bhāṣya* can tell us about their historical circumstances, and how the aims of the author(s) can be linked to the social history of the Jaina community. For this purpose, I will focus on the language and rhetorical strategies of the texts in the light of the historical evidence of the Jainas in the Gupta Period.

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February 2018

Epic Narratives in India and Asia

Dr Sven Bretfeld (NTNU Trondheim), Dr Csaba Dezső (Eötvös Loránd University), Dr Laxshmi Greaves (Leiden), Dr Kevin McGrath (Harvard), Dr Ulrike Roesler (Oxford), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 13 February 2018

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 13 February 2018

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: Senate House

Room: S116

Outlining the Bhārata, Vyāsa's First Poem

Dr Kevin McGrath (Harvard)

The paper examines the use of two terms used by the poets: 'jaya' and 'dhyāna'. The first of these words is shown to indicate the earliest rendering of the poem; then, the argument is developed to demonstrate how such a primary work was initially inspired. The second term, 'dhyāna', is shown to lie at the basis of Vyāsa's compositional technique; the word also uniquely occurs in relation to two of the heroes, Kṛṣṇa and Bhīṣma, whom I argue are characters who are crucial to the narrative formation of the epic. This final ordering however, concerns not so much the act of inspiration but of early textual 'edition'.

The Tibetan Rāmāyaṇa(s): the Story of Rāma and Sītā, or the Story of Rāma and Rāvaṇa?

Dr Ulrike Roesler (Oxford)

While the spread of the *Rāmāyaṇa* into South East Asia is well-known and well-documented, the spread into Central Asia is documented in a fairly haphazard way through fragments in various languages, including Khotanese, Uighur, and Tocharian. The most complete version, however, is the Tibetan Rāma story preserved among the Dunhuang manuscripts.

A closer investigation of these Tibetan fragments comes to the following conclusions: a) The Tibetan *Rāmāyaṇa* was intended as a heroic epic, and the true heroes are Rāma and Rāvaṇa, rather than Rāma and Sītā. b) The Tibetan Rāma story from

Dunhuang shares certain elements with the *Rāmāyaṇa* tradition in South East Asia and must therefore be understood as part of this wider tradition. c) Later literary adaptations of the Rāma story composed in Tibet between the 13th and 20th centuries seem to follow the story line of the Dunhuang version; the Rāma story from Dunhuang has thus had a long-lasting impact on Tibetan literature, even if the fragments themselves had been hidden away until their re-discovery in the 20th century.

Responses by

Dr Csaba Dezső (Eötvös Loránd University), "The Character of Sītā in Gupta-Period Kāvya Literature"

Dr Laxshmi Greaves (Leiden), "Epic Stories in Terracotta Plaques"

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March 2018

Kucha in the 4th-6th century CE: A Kingdom Rising on the Silk Road

Dr Chao-jung Ching 慶昭蓉 (Centre de Recherche sur les Civilisations de l'Asie Orientale)

Date: 13 March 2018

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 13 March 2018

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: The Wesley Hotel, 81-103 Euston Street, NW1 2EZ Room: Maathai Room

After the fall of Eastern Han dynasty in 220 CE and the decline of Kushan Empire due to Sasanian invasions around the mid 3rd century, the oasis states around the Taklamakan Desert (Xinjiang, China) faced a kind of power vacuum between their East and West. Many local rulers were soon subordinated to the more powerful ones among them, i.e. Qiuci (Kucha) and Yanqi (Karashar) to the north, Shanshan to the south-east, Yutian (Khotan) to the south and Shule (Kashgar) to the west. Although the post-Han history of Kucha was rather obscure until the Tang Conquest of its capital in 648 CE, evidently it became one of the most powerful "Buddhist kingdoms" on the Silk Road in the 4th-6th century, as witnessed by splendid Buddhist grottoes that still survive in situ to this day.

In this talk, I shall explore the rise of Kucha from a historical perspective. Attention will be paid on various Kharoṣṭhī material collected in this region, written in a local variant of Gāndhārī, as well as Brāhmī texts written in the Kuchean language (also known as Tocharian B). In particular, I shall reflect the traffic on the Silk Road around this main station, as well as its interactions with certain nomadic neighbors to its north.

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April 2018

Revisiting the Traikūṭakas and Historical Problems in Western India

Prof Hans T. Bakker (British Museum), Dr Dániel Balogh (British Museum), Francesco Bianchini (Oxford), Dr Serena Biondo (British Museum), Robert Bracey (British Museum), Dr Gethin Rees (British Library), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 10 April 2018 Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 10 April 2018 Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: Senate House Room: S118

This workshop will re-examine the chronology of the dynasties of western and central India, with special emphasis on the dating of the Traikūṭakas and their records. Although the Traikūṭakas are not known as one of the 'great powers' of the period, the content and dating of their inscriptions has wide implications for the development of Indian religious ideas and texts.

Position papers by

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), "Introduction: the *Mahābhārata* and Vaiṣṇava faith in early central India"

Prof Hans T. Bakker (British Museum), "V. V. Mirashi and the Kalacuri Cedi era"

Dr Dániel Balogh (British Museum), "The early Rāṣṭrakūṭas of the Deccan"

Francesco Bianchini (Oxford), "The Maitrakas and some of their early records"

Dr Serena Biondo (British Museum), "Varṣamāsavrata in India and Nepal"

Robert Bracey (British Museum), "Numismatics and Traikūṭaka history"

Dr Gethin Rees (British Library), "Kanheri inscriptions"

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May 2018

Newar Buddhism and Hinduism

Prof Alexander von Rospatt (UC Berkeley) and Dr Jessica Vantine Birkenholtz (University of Illinois)

Date: 8 May 2018

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 8 May 2018

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings

Room: 116

The Svayambhūpurāṇa and the religious landscape of medieval Buddhism in Nepal it paints

Prof Alexander von Rospatt (UC Berkeley)

Among the Buddhist narrative works produced in Sanskrit in Nepal in the 15th and 16th centuries, the *Svayambhūpurāṇa* stands out as an original composition that draws upon mythological themes and legends in order to offer—in the absence of a vibrant Buddhist tradition in India proper—a novel vision of the historical Nepal Valley as the true motherland of Buddhism. In the process it draws a picture of Nepalese Buddhism and its history that allows to behold the tradition on its own terms. The talk will offer an overview of the different versions of the *Svayambhūpurāṇa*, including pictorial depictions, introduce to its principal themes and explore how it evolved over time to incorporate new materials and perspectives.

A history of Nepali Hinduism as told through the pages of the Svasthanivratākatha
Dr Jessica Vantine Birkenholtz (University of Illinois)

This talk employs Nepal's *Svasthanivratākatha* text as a lens to explore the heterogeneous landscape of Newar Hinduism in medieval Nepal and the shift toward a singular, hegemonic form of high-caste hill, or Parbatiya, Hinduism in modern Nepal. The *Svasthanivratākatha* originated in the sixteenth century as a folk legend among Nepal's indigenous Newar Hindus. By the early twentieth century, the text had become an expansive Purana text, which reflected the emergence of a broader—but simultaneously narrower, Brahmanical—'Hindu' identity that became increasingly important for the Parbatiya ruling elite in modern Nepal. The talk examines the contours and transformations of the *Svasthanivratākatha*, first, to highlight key aspects of medieval Newar religion and culture and, second, to demonstrate the impact of Parbatiya Hinduism thereupon in modern Nepal. Finally, the talk argues that the *Svasthanivratākatha*'s development reflects a privileging of Nepali Hindu-ness to create a shared Nepali Hindu tradition and identity.

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June 2018

Insults and Apologies in Early Indian Buddhism: The Etiquette of Everyday Monasticism
Dr Christopher Handy (Leiden)

Date: 12 June 2018 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 12 June 2018 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Senate House Room: S118

The behaviour of ordained monastics in the earliest days of the Indian Buddhist tradition was carefully regulated by a code of law called vinaya. This genre of Sanskrit and Pāli literature includes much material on ethics (*śīla/sīla*), which is how monastic law is traditionally explained. However, social face and its public performance are an equally important component of monastic law. Many vinaya injunctions in the Indian Buddhist literary tradition demonstrate proper etiquette through frame stories depicting interactions between monastics and their grumpy patrons. Buddhists inherited most of their ideas on normative social face from a majority tradition of Brahmanism, with many

rules expressly created to mitigate the complaints of the laity. In this presentation, I focus on polite and impolite speech acts described in vinaya narratives, and especially the concepts of insults and apologies. These episodes represent the concept of "right speech" in Buddhism, and can also be traced back to earlier Vedic concepts of proper speech. I consider whether these rules represent a code of ethics, of pragmatism, or a mixture of both.

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July 2018 – No Workshop

August 2018 – No Workshop

September 2018

Upland societies and lowland polities in Asia

Dr Cristina Bignami (Tübingen), Dr Daniela De Simone (British Museum), Dr Letizia Trinco (La Sapienza, University of Rome), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 11 September 2018	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 11 September 2018	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Paul Webley Wing (Senate House)	Room: S211

The study of the relationship between upland societies and lowland polities is in its early stages within Asian studies. Historians have tended to focus on the development of lowland polities centred on royal and ritual sites with their monumental remains, and the concurrent emergence of religions, technologies, agriculture and trade. Upland societies stand apart, although they have played an important role in Asia in the *longue durée*. The theoretical framework created by James Scott for the study of upland societies in South East Asia and the methodological approaches developed by Subaltern Studies for data collection and analysis of marginal social groups have significantly contributed to the debate on the pre-modern history of Asia. However, their theories and approaches have proved limited to determine what role upland societies played in the making of Asia. This workshop will focus on the nature and content of the upland-lowland exchange, the features of upland language, archaeology and culture, and the theoretical and practical methodologies that might be deployed in South Asia to foster a compelling interdisciplinary approach.

Position papers by

Dr Daniela De Simone (British Museum), "Of forest-dwellers, wild animals and spices: towards an archaeology and pre-colonial history of Indian upland forests"

Dr Cristina Bignami (Tübingen), "Kings of the wild"

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), "Highland collections, archaeology and the archaeology of religion"

Dr Letizia Trinco (La Sapienza, University of Rome), "Hero-stones: what tradition, whose tradition? Reflections on the liminality of some funerary monuments in South Asia"

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October 2018

Famines, Earthquakes and Climate Events

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum) and Dr Christopher Davis (Durham)

Date: 9 October 2018 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 9 October 2018 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

Severe periods of drought interspersed with intense monsoons are known now to have been factors that contributed to the decline and eventual demise of Angkor Wat and Khmer civilisation in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries. This workshop will focus on the evidence for similar events in South Asia and the religious and political impacts they had between circa 1000 and 1300. This was a period when the cultural dispensation established in the 4th and 5th centuries suffered a series of well-known existential shocks. In addition, evidence for major earthquakes in the same centuries will be examined. The aim of the workshop will be to explore methodologies for verifying the scope and nature of these catastrophic events.

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), *Māṇḍu and Old Māṇḍu: Hinterland Cities in Historical Context*

Dr Christopher Davis (Durham), *Earthquake Effects and Seismic Resilience in Medieval Nepal: New Evidence from Post-Disaster Archaeological Investigations in the Kathmandu Valley*

Round table discussion chaired by Prof Hans T. Bakker (British Museum) and Prof Janice Stargardt (Cambridge)

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November 2018

Bodhgayā: Collections and Archives

Dr Sam van Schaik (British Library), Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), Dr Daniela Simone (British Museum), Dr Daniël Balogh (British Museum) and Dr Marc Miyake (British Museum)

Date: 13 November 2018 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 13 November 2018 Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

This workshop will review recent research and discoveries related to Bodhgayā. Drawing on the collections and archival material in the British Library, British Museum and V&A, team members and project collaborators will have an opportunity to present recent findings that will be included in a volume to be published by British Museum Press. The working title is *Precious Treasures from the Diamond Throne*. The workshop will be an opportunity to see how different contributions to the volume relate and overlap, and to develop potential synergies across the forthcoming book.

Dr Sam van Schaik (British Library), *Tibetan Visitors to Bodhgayā in the 11th to 13th centuries*

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), *Copper-plates and Precious Gems: Recent Findings*

Dr Daniela Simone (British Museum) and Dr Daniël Balogh (British Museum), *The Earliest Evidence: the Āsana at Bodhgayā*

Dr Marc Miyake (British Museum) and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), *The Old Mon Tablets from Bodhgayā*

In the roundtable discussion that will follow the presentations, teams members will have an opportunity to discuss their recent discoveries relating to Bodhgaya and themes more generally across the project.

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December 2018

Cults of Viṣṇu in Early India

Prof Hans T. Bakker (British Museum), Dr Dániel Balogh (British Museum), Francesco Bianchini (Oxford), Dr Serena Biondo (British Museum), Dr Gergely Hidas (British Museum), Dr Marion Rastelli (Vienna), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 11 December 2018 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 11 December 2018 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

The cult of Viṣṇu was promoted by the Gupta kings and it is probably thanks to them that Viṣṇu became associated with kingship. An important ritual in this regard was the *varṣāmāsavrata*. This celebrated Viṣṇu's four months of sleep during the rainy season and integrates concepts of kingship with cosmological themes and the cycles of the seasons. In central India, inscriptions and images document the extent of this ritual in Gupta times. When Gupta power started to decline, at the end of the fifth century and into the sixth, we find evidence of the *varṣāmāsavrata* in South India and Nepal. This decentralised movement suggests a search among the Vaiṣṇava priesthood for new sponsors. In addition to archaeological evidence, the *Viṣṇudharmāḥ* is key. Drawing on established Vaiṣṇava traditions, this text describes the modes of worship and the

duties and the eventual rewards of Vaiṣṇava devotees. This workshop provides an opportunity to discuss archaeological and textual evidence to better understand the spread of the cult of Viṣṇu, the individuals who promoted it and the factors that facilitated its reception.

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum), Early Evidence: the Varṣāmāsavrata in Central India and the Deccan

Francesco Bianchini (Oxford), Viṣṇu and his forms in royal praśastis from Western India

Dr Serena Biondo (British Museum), The Varṣāmāsavrata Ritual in Nepal
Sanne Mersch (Leiden), A Viṣṇustotra in the Skandapurāṇa: an outsider's perspective on Viṣṇu and Vaiṣṇava mythology

Dr Marion Rastelli (Austrian Academy of Sciences), Worshipping Viṣṇu's Twelve Manifestations: A Glimpse into Early Medieval Vaiṣṇava Lay Practice

Dr Nirajan Kafle (Leiden), On the date of the Viṣṇudharma

Dr Gergely Hidas (British Museum), The Varṣāmāsavrata chapter of the Viṣṇudharma and Buddhist rainmaking rituals

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January 2019

Further Insights into Early Tantric Buddhism from the Dunhuang Manuscripts
Prof Jake Dalton (Berkeley)

This presentation offers a more 'literary' approach to early tantric Buddhist ritual manuals. Elsewhere I have argued that ritual manuals spread as a new genre in orthodox Buddhist circles from the mid-fifth through the sixth centuries. Dunhuang, as a kind of time capsule of such early manuals, offers valuable insights into the development of the genre. Close readings of the language used in the tantric manuals in particular suggest that poetic language—metaphor, rhythm, rhyme, etc.—often marks key moments in the ritual proceedings. In such passages, poetic language is deployed to create specific affective experiences in the reader/ritualist.

Date: 8 January 2019 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 8 January 2019 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

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February 2019

Translation, Transmission and Manuscripts

Michael Willis (British Museum), Matt Kimberley (British Library) and Fabrizio Speziale (CNRS)

Date: 12 February 2019

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 12 February 2019

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: Paul Webley Wing (Senate House)

Room: S211

This workshop will examine the twin processes of translation and transmission, with special focus on texts and manuscripts in the British Library. While translations of Buddhist works are documented from the early centuries CE by Chinese examples, and slightly later from Tibetan texts, close knowledge of the manuscripts and individuals involved are known best from later cases, notably the translations undertaken at the Mughal court in India. As with all such projects, close scrutiny of manuscripts, and what is recorded in them and about them historically, reveals much about the nature of the translation activity and the complex web of assumptions that have informed the creation of modern editions and studies.

Matt Kimberley (British Library) *Medicine on the Silk Road: Khotanese sources for the transmission of Indian medical traditions*

Khotan played a central role in the transmission of Buddhism from India to China and Tibet during the first millennium CE. In addition, Buddhism is cited frequently as the vehicle by which Indian medicine was transmitted to South, Central and East Asia. By examining the textual sources from Khotan – and Khotanese sources elsewhere in Central Asia – it may be possible to construct a partial history of the role that Khotan played in the spread of medical knowledge.

Michael Willis (British Museum), *Translations and Histories: Persian Texts of the Mahābhārata in the British Library*

The *Mahābhārata* is India's national epic, a massive text that took its present form in the fifth century CE. In 1582, the Mughal emperor Akbar (1542-1605) commissioned a translation of the *Mahābhārata* from Sanskrit into Persian. While this was just one of several translations sponsored by the Mughal court, it was the most ambitious and occupied a team of Muslim and Hindu scholars until 1584. This paper will seek to discuss the names of the scholars involved, the different views of the project at court and the nature of the *Mahābhārata* available in 1582, and how the text was treated by the editors of the Tehran edition.

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